

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON APPROACH OF MANAGEMENT STUDENTS TOWARDS ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A CAREER ORIENTATION

¹Pallavi

Assistant Professor
Department of Management Studies
SSA Government First Grade College(Autonomous)
Ballari, Karnataka

²Shivanath E G

Assistant Professor
Department of Management Studies
Government First Grade College, Ripponpet
Hosanagara, Shimoga, Karnataka

ABSTRACT

The views of young generation about “Entrepreneurship” are serious matter of concern because most of the students have aspiration of getting salaried job and are not interested to start own venture . There is a general tendency that if somebody does not get job then only he or she will go for some kind of business activity. In our society many people consider business as the last option of career and the first preference will go to a paid job. Management students running behind the salaried jobs though they are having business management skills to start their own venture; it seems failure of management education. Management education has an important place; but how to make it more favourable to develop entrepreneurship is the area of prime concern. In this paper researches has tried to find out the reasons for choosing salaried job over entrepreneurship and vice versa. The primary data of sample of 100 management students has been collected. The collected data was in discrete categorical form hence simple percentile analysis of the data is been carried out. According to the researcher that the students who developed business administration skills through the management education do not try to start their own venture instead they prefer to pocket salaried job the reason being socioeconomic pressure.

Key Words: Management Education, Entrepreneurship, salaried Job, socioeconomic pressure

1. INTRODUCTION

Indian Universities are getting approximately 5 lack students enrolment in the management stream every year. All of them have a hope to get employed in the thriving economy. Most of the aspirants may be settling their hope to get a good job of their choice and the rest of students hope for different opportunity of earning money. The different opportunity could be various kinds of business activities. The percentage of students wanted to start up a business of their own is very less compared to those who give preference

to paid/salaried job. At present Indian economy is growing at the rate of 7.1%, ample of opportunities available for graduates to start a business. The tendency of Indian management students is to get placed in highly paid corporate jobs, which is un expected from them because management education supports them o become entrepreneur. What is the main hindrance in creating entrepreneurs? . Is it an un updated Indian education system or socio cultural factors which are obstructing a business student to start his or her own business.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Arshad Nabi Wani (GRA – Global Research Analysis, Volume2, Issue 5, May 2013)

This paper focuses on the role played by educational institutions towards entrepreneurship development. The Researcher has been chosen as a case study for said purpose. This paper tries to explain that why entrepreneurship has not been the career choice of the students. It also focuses on the importance of entrepreneurs in economic development. Moreover this paper tries to focus on the strategies to be adopted by the Educational Institutes to focus on entrepreneurship education, research and development. The researcher has conducted exploratory type of research. This paper concludes that Educational institutes have a significant role to play in promoting entrepreneurship. They are actually the nurseries where the students are to shape their careers. Entrepreneurs are necessary for the growth of any nation. They create jobs for themselves and for others. The findings prove that the University of Kashmir has not been able to promote entrepreneurship education. Promoting entrepreneurship education will help us to inculcate an entrepreneurial spirit among our youth. It is the high time the university starts courses on entrepreneurship.

Devi R. Gnyawali, Daniel S. Fogel (Entrepreneurship Theory And Practice · July 1994)

This paper develops such a framework consisting of five dimensions of entrepreneurial environments and links these dimensions to the core elements of the new venture creation process. Specific emphasis is given to the role of environmental conditions in developing opportunities and in enhancing entrepreneurs' propensity and ability to enterprise. The paper outlines some propositions and research implications of the integrated model and offers initial guidelines for formulating public policies to develop entrepreneurial environments.

First, Researcher had attempted to include major environmental conditions empirically studied or mentioned in the existing literature. Second, we show interrelationships among these conditions. Third, and most importantly, we have attempted to develop a parsimonious framework that captures the richness of an entrepreneurial environment and can be subjected to systematic research. Researchers grouped the environmental conditions into five dimensions: government policies and procedures, socioeconomic conditions, entrepreneurial and business skills, financial support to businesses, and non-financial support to businesses. Researcher has developed a useful model to advance these arguments. He believed that the model and testable propositions developed in this paper will be useful for researchers interested in studying entrepreneurial environments and for practitioners involved in designing and improving policies and programs for entrepreneurship development.

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Dr.Sushmita B Waraich, Renu Sharma (AIMA Journal of Management & Research, November 2012, Volume 6, Issue 4/4, ISSN 0974-497)

This paper explores the linkage between management education and entrepreneurship, whether B-schools can create/discover entrepreneurs, the content and relevance of entrepreneurship courses at B-schools and the significance of incubator programs in B-schools. For the purpose of this qualitative research, 22 entrepreneurs were interviewed, their views taken and analyzed. This paper concludes that there is agreement to a great degree that management education would lead to entrepreneurship though some of the respondents were of the view that the constraints faced by entrepreneurs in India are many and could deter the entrepreneurship drive. A majority were of the view that instead of being a part of general management education it should be a distinct stream/course in management. Almost half of the respondents opined that a lot depends on the students' parents i.e. whether they are themselves self-employed or not. Comparatively, more than fifty per cent of the entrepreneurs were of the view that in order to create that atmosphere and entrepreneurial attitude, entrepreneurship education should be introduced right at the higher secondary/under graduation level. The curriculum of entrepreneurship education should include more of practical exposure with enough scope for innovation. The business incubator programs though at a nascent stage in India do provide the right direction to start a new enterprise as well as to become visible among venture capitalists and angel funding.

Dr. N. Kishore Babu, K. Vidyasagar, (International Journal of Academic Research Vol.2, Issue-2(7), April-June, 2015)

In this paper Researcher has conducted exploratory study. This paper attempts to explain the evolution of entrepreneurship education in India. It then discusses the importance and role of entrepreneurship in Indian Economy; it further discusses the challenges regard to the role of educational programs and delivery systems for disseminating these entrepreneurship education programs. This paper tries to explain the role of B-Schools in shaping and nurturing of future entrepreneurs in India. It also discusses whether current curriculum taught in b-school meets the requirement of building entrepreneurs. This paper concludes that Entrepreneurship, self-employment and enterprise creation provide a solution to the crises of both unemployment and under-employment. The B-Schools help in increasing knowledge base, by identifying opportunities, and by pointing out ways to overcome barriers imposed by ones environment. They have a definite role in enhancing entrepreneurship by enlarging the pool of entrepreneurs in society. Therefore, the Indian government should take appropriate measures to promote and develop entrepreneurial education in India.

Prof. Jaladi Ravi, Bhanotu Venkateswara Rao P. Satya Vara Prasad (International Journal of Academic Research Vol.2, Issue-2(7), April-June, 2015)

In this paper researcher has discussed the role of management education system in developing entrepreneurs based on secondary data. The researcher concludes that for management education to successfully contribute to entrepreneurship development there are several factors which should be kept in mind. While selecting students majority of the students should be selected who have the ability to take risks and the initiative to be on their own. Secondly, there should be a blend of experienced academic faculty members for theoretical base as well as entrepreneurs on board in order to have practical exposure. Apart from classroom education, their attitudinal training, in entrepreneurship should go hand

in hand especially bringing out that confidence to engage. They should be exposed to enough of real life situations by participating in business plan competitions on a regular basis, handling live industry projects more often and the like. Successful entrepreneurs should be roped in, to share their experiences with the students – things like challenges faced by them, opportunities in the market, knowledge about financial assistance. More and more interaction with entrepreneurs through guest lectures and seminars/conferences and close association with senior managers in high growth, innovative companies would go a long way in enlightening the future entrepreneurs. By being associated with entrepreneurs the desire to start a new venture becomes more intense. Last but not the least, both government as well as private entities should take active interest in nurturing the entrepreneurial venture.

SaadatSaeed, Moreno Muffatto and ShumailaYousafzai (De Gruyterdoi 10.1515/erj-2013-0041 ERJ 2014; 4(3): 297–321)

This study examines how a university's support impacts students' entrepreneurial intentions and finds that entrepreneurship education, concept development support, and business-development support increase such intentions. A sample of 805 undergraduate students in universities in Pakistan took part in the study. The university role is critical to the growth of entrepreneurial intentions, and researcher argues that an individual's decision in favor of or against becoming an entrepreneur depends on the multi-level context provided by the university. Researcher's findings suggest that students perceive the education and concept-development support (educational and cognitive) from their universities as highly influential on their entrepreneurial intentions. This paper concludes that a multi-level perspective offers a meaningful understanding of entrepreneurship and offer suggestions for university management and policy-makers for enhancing entrepreneurship.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The tendency is among management students that they look forward to highly paid jobs while pursuing their management education. This is not expected from the students of management studies because their educational background supports them to become entrepreneur. The obvious reason why management students are inclined towards highly paid jobs while pursuing their management education is that, the various management institutes are marketing themselves as a ticket to lucrative jobs with high pay packages. It is a contrast according to the researcher that the students who developed business administration skills through the management education do not try to start their own venture instead they prefer to pocket salaried job the reason being peer and family pressure. The researcher found it interesting to study whether it is possible to make more number of entrepreneurs among the students of management education by studying the student's preference about entrepreneurship over salaried job.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive and empirical type of research which includes surveys and fact-finding enquires of different kinds. The major purpose of this research is the description of the state of affairs as it exists at present. The empirical research relies on experience or observation alone, often without due regard for system and theory. Suitable statistical techniques are used to analyse the data.

4.1. Objectives

1. To find out the motives behind preferring salaried job over entrepreneurship
2. To understand the factors influencing entrepreneurship as a career over salaried job

4.2. Scope of the Research

The research study was conducted in the University of Bangalore in Karnataka state. 56 MBA colleges are affiliated to Bangalore University. There are students from all over India pursuing their management education in Bangalore University. The student respondents are from varied socioeconomic background.

Period of Research – Year 2016 to 2018

During this period of time 100 management students from the management institutes under the Bangalore University are surveyed.

Target Group - Management Students who are getting formal education in management from Bangalore University.

4.3. Sample Design

The study is carried out by considering convenience sampling method. The total research sample is divided into two stage sampling as detailed below.

Sample-I: Survey of management students from industrial background pursuing their management education in the first year.

Sample-II: Survey of second year management students being placed in campus recruitment with lucrative salary.

4.3.1. Sample Size:

100 number of respondents from various management institutions under Bangalore University.

4.4. Data Collection

Primary data collection- Primary data is collected through the personal interviews with the help of structured questionnaires

Secondary data collection- Secondary data is collected from various journals, books, research papers, and concerned websites.

4.5. Analysis of the Data

After the data have been collected a number of closely related operations such as establishment of categories, the application of these categories to raw data through coding & tabulation are done and then statistical inferences are drawn.

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The collected data was in discrete categorical form hence simple percentile analysis of the data is done. The various variables are analyzed based on their frequency of occurrence. The cross tabulation analysis of various variables is done to understand the association between the respective variables.

4.6. Limitations of the Study

The research is carried out in the colleges affiliated to Bangalore University hence the various parameters considered during the research may or may not exist at different places other than Bangalore University.

5. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The attitude towards management students about Entrepreneurship are matter of concern because 70% of the students have aspiration of getting salaried job and are not interested to start own business . 30% of students are interested in starting up a business. Indian students consider business as the last option of career and the first preference will go to a paid job.

Fig.5.1

Having confirmed that only 30% of the students have entrepreneurial intentions, researcher had tried to figure out which were the motives driving them to start an own business. The notable observation made was this 30% set of students who opted entrepreneurship as a career are the respondents having considerable industrial experience before joining the management course. Researcher has listed 15 possible reasons which may influence students to start a business. The major reasons to become entrepreneur are to use technical or Professional knowledge and skills and to give birth their brain child “an own start up”. To researchers surprise students does not fear the unemployment neither they strive for social status nor they want to utilise their idle funds. These are the last preferred options from the respondents.

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Fig. 5.2

In the backdrop of booming economy the management education is becoming the source of attraction to student’s community. The reason being management students are getting placed in lucrative high profile jobs even before completing their management programme. Career decision is very complicated especially for management students. They are always served with two plates, first one with highly paid job and another with chasing the dream of starting own business, the latter always get surpassed by the

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prior because of various reasons. Researcher has listed possible 13 reasons which may influence the students to prefer salaried job over entrepreneurship.

Students prefer job over entrepreneurship because of family pressure, to earn social status, to maintain work life balance. Every management student is taught to take risk. They do not fear of taking risk but their set back is family pressure to earn for them. No seed capital to start a business. Many of them think a job gives a decent social status and work life balance where in business requires more attention which causes imbalance in personal life.

Fig. 5.3

6. FINDINGS

- Present management students are becoming relatively more number of managers to work for others and very few job creators i.e. entrepreneurs.
- Management students want to start a business to use their skills and abilities as entrepreneurs
- The socioeconomic parameters can influence the career decision of students
- The career planning of student is linked with the expectation of family.
- Lack of initial capital is a major reason to start a own business

7. CONCLUSION

Students are infatuated by the fat salary jobs in market. Pursuing professional education is considered as a passport to get a handsome salaried job. The parents don't want their children to take risk at the initial stage of career,

8. SUGGESTIONS

The present management education system can be made more oriented to build up confidence in the minds of students that they can become successful entrepreneurs. They can lead balance work life and have social security.

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